

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1975	Алена Тазранова	1995	2002		w	Russian philologist (тюркология, алтайский язык, малочисленные языки, язык чалканцев, теленгитский диалект, синтаксис, морфология)	
1975	Paul de Lacy	1996	2002			American linguist	
1975	Michael Wesch	1997	2004			American associate professor of cultural anthropology	
1975	Tamás Sándor Biró	1997	2006			Hungarian computational linguist (Mathematical and computational linguistics, Optimality Theory, cognitive approaches to culture, Hebrew and Semitic linguistics)	
1975	Timur Maisak	1997	2002			Russian linguist	
1975	Steve Pasek	1997	2012			German Egyptologist, Demotist, Historian and Classicist	
1975	Anuradha Bhattacharyya	1998	2005		w	Indian Associate Professor of English Literature (fiction, poetry, writing)	
1975	Eugen Ciurtin	1998	2000			Romanian researcher & secretary, Institute for the History of Religions	
1975	Ana Jelnikar	1999	2009		w	Slovenian culturologist (cultural and literary connections between India and Slovenia)	
1975	Urmás Nommik	1999	2009			Estonian Associate Professor of Old Testament and Semitic Studies	
1975	Sebastian Domsch	2000	2003			Germanish Professor of Anglophone Literature and Culture	
1975	Vincenzo Lomiento	2000	2004			Italian Researcher of Ancient Christian Literature	
1975	Мацько Оксана Михайлівна	2000	2001		w	Ukrainian Associate Professor of the Department of Ukrainian Language and Applied Linguistics	
1975	Cornelia Rémi	2001	2004		w	Austrian Assistant Professor of German Literature	
1975	Dr. Mahdi Inaayah Kareem al-Utbi	2001	2008			Iraqi Professor of Linguistics	
1975	Lucija Ljubić	2001	2009		w	Croatian President of the Chair in Cultural Studies (theatrology and arts)	
1975	Paul Catanese	2001	No			American Professor, Director of Graduate Study, Art & Art History (Hybrid media art)	
1975	Alexis Michaud	2001	2017			French linguist (outheast Asian languages, especially Naic languages and Vietnamese)	

1975 Florian Schäfer	2002	2007		German linguist	
1975 Jasim Al-Maryani	2002	2016		Iraqi Assistant Professor of Translation and Interpreting	
1975 Purificação Silvano	2002	2002	w	Portuguese Professor of Linguistics	
1975 Heather Hurst	2002	2009	w	American archaeologist and archaeological illustrator	
1975 Stine Rossel	2002	2007	2007 w	Danish postdoc and Instructor of Egyptology	1975-2007
1975 Francesca Stavrakopoulou	2002	2002	w	British Professor of Hebrew Bible and Ancient Religion	
1975 Ana Vujanović	2003	2004	w	Serbian freelance cultural researcher, writer, lecturer, dramaturge (performing arts)	
1975 Atinati Mamatsashvili	2003	2006	w	Georgian Professor in Comparative Literature (Comparative and French Literature, totalitarian regimes and literature, anti-Semitism)	
1975 Ermina Ramadanovic	2003	2012	2017 w	Croatian research assistant at the Institute for Croatian Language and Linguistics at the Department of Lexicography	1975-2017
1975 Stavroula Constantinou	2003	2003	w	Cypriot academic who specialises in Byzantine literature	
1975 Колесник Олександр Сергійович	2003			Ukrainian professor of Germanic Philology	
1975 Wafaa El Beih	2003	2003		Egyptian Professor of Photography	
1975 Samsul Maarif	2003	2012		Indonesian Secretary, and lecturer of Center for Religious and Cross-cultural Studies/CRCS	
1975 Hedde Zeijlstra	2004	2004		Dutch Professor of Linguistics	
1975 Myrto Garani	2004	2004	w	Greek Assistant Professor in Latin Literature	
1975 Dorothy King	2004	2013	w	American author and archeologist	
1975 Dolly Kikon	2004	2013	w	Australian Naga Anthropologist	
1975 Masiwa Ragies Gunda	2004	2005		Zimbabwean the Old Testament and biblical hebrew scholar	
1975 Elizabeth Allison	2004	2009	w	American Associate Professor of Ecology and Religion	
1975 Ilgim Veryeri Alaca	2005	2005	w	Turkish Assistant Professor at Department of Media and Visual Arts	
1975 Robyn Rodriguez	2005	2005	w	Filipino American professor, author, and activist	
1975 Tofantšuk	2007	2007	w	Estonian Associate Professor of British Literature at the School of Humanities	

1975 Zakayo Iworete Amayi	2007	No		Kenyan Lecturer of Literature (Trauma Studies in Literature, Literary, Theory and Criticism, Global literature)
1975 Maha al-Senan	2007	2009	w	Saudi Arabian art historian
1975 Arwa Abdulrasoul Salman Ibrahim	2008	2008	w	Iraqi Assistant Professor In English language and Linguistics (Phonetics & Phonology)
1975 Foteini Vlachou	2008	2013	w	Greek archaeologist and art historian
1975 Mohamad Fleih Hassan	2008	2017		Iraqi Assistant Professor in English Literature
1975 Tolga Zafer Özdemir	2008	2008		Turkish symphonic music composer and musicologist
1975 Anna Foka	2009	2009	w	Greek Associate Professor, Scientific Leader Digital Humanities
1975 Farhang Muzaffar Muhamad	2009	2010		Kurdish Assistant Professor of Literature
1975 Devrim Akman	2010	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1975 Oluwole Adefemi	2015	No		Nigerian Lecturer of Department of Languages and Linguistics (media studies, advertising, public relations, cinematography, development and health communications)
1975 Anthony Le Duc	2015			Vietnamese-American Fellow of Asian Research Center for Religion and Social Communication
1976 Stef Craps	1996	2003		Belgian professor of English literature
1976 Gunther Martens	1998	2003		Belgian Professor of German Literature
1976 Petja Grafenauer	1998	2010	w	Slovenian art historian, contemporary art curator, art critic, editor and publicist
1976 Kozma Ahačič	1998	2007		Slovenian linguist and literary historian
1976 Mila Maeva	1998	2005	w	Bulgarian ethnologist (ethnography, anthropology, emigration, Turkish culture, Islam)
1976 Dagmar Abfalter	1999	2008	w	Austrian Associate Professor at the Department of Cultural Management and Gender Studies
1976 Tamara Wagner	1999	2002	w	British Associate Professor of English Literature (Victorian Literature)
1976 Jeroen van Craenenbroeck	1999	2004		Dutch linguist
1976 Dag Haug	2000	2001		Norwegian linguist

1976	Dahlia Schweitzer	2000	2013	w	American associate professor in the Film and Media Department at the Fashion Institute of Technology
1976	Daniel Dejica	2000	2009		Romanian professor in translation studies
1976	Diana-Adriana Lefter	2000	2016	w	Romanian assoc. prf phd.HDR, Language and Literature Department
1976	Gerardo Rodríguez-Salas	2000	2003		Spanish Senior Lecturer in English Literature
1976	Halim Rane	2000	2012		Australian Islamic studies scholar
1976	Paola Escudero	2000	2005	w	Peruan Associate Professor In Linguistics, Marcs Institute For Brain
1976	Piotr Marecki	2000	2007		Polish assistant professor, lecturer at the Polish National Film, Television and Theater
1976	Sead Nazibegović	2000	2009		Bosnian Associate Professor at the UNO Linguistics of Bosnian Language and Literature
1976	Seth Cluett	2000	2013		Columbian composer and visual artist
1976	Tom Mole	2000	2003		British Professor of English Literature and Book History
1976	Georgiy Starostin	2000	2000		Russian linguist (comparative linguistics, historical linguistics, Nostratics, Proto-World)
1976	Valentina Velkovska - Trajanovska	2000		w	North Macedonian Professor of Music Art
1976	Romain Garnier	2000	2004		French linguist (Indo-European linguistics)
1976	Aaron D. Rubin	2000	2004		American linguistics researcher
1976	Melinda Torok	2000	No	w	Serbian artist in Fine Art
1976	Sarojini Nadar	2000	2003	w	South African Full Professor: Gender and Religion Program
1976	Epp Lankots	2000	2014	w	Estonian Vice Rector for Research at Institute of Art History and Visual Culture
1976	Gönül Gökdemir Reyhanoğlu	2001	2008	w	Turkish Assistant Professor of Turkish Language and Literature
1976	JJH Klooster	2001	2008	w	Dutch assistant professor of Greek literature
1976	Marko Liker	2001	2009		Croatian Assistant professor of Department of Phonetics
1976	Fridrik Dulaj	2001	2012		Albanian professor of Literature and Language
1976	Jelena Kallas	2002	2013	w	Estonian computational lexicographer

1976	Kristine Steenbergh	2002	2007	w	Dutch lecturer and researcher in early modern English drama
1976	Murat Cankara	2002	2011		Turkish professor of Faculty in Turkish Language and Literature
1976	Patrick Mason	2002	2005		American historian, the Leonard J. Arrington Chair of Mormon History and Culture
1976	Uwe Reichel	2002	2010		German linguist (phonetician)
1976	Victoria Flanagan	2002	2005	w	Australian Senior Lecturer in Children's Literature
1976	Karen Stollznow	2002	2007	w	Australian-American writer, linguist, and skeptic
1976	Benedikt Szmrecsanyi	2003	2005		German linguist
1976	Danillo Barata	2003	2012		Brazilian visual painter, curator, and professor of arts (combines performance and image, and focuses on the relationship between the body, the camera, the art system, and the world)
1976	Julian Kreimer	2003	No		American Associate Professor of Art and Design (painter, art critic, and educator)
1976	Miroslava Gavurová	2003	2003	w	Slovakian linguist and literature critic, translator (poetry, children's books and fiction)
1976	Rebecca N. Mitchell	2003	2006	w	American Reader in Victorian Literature and Culture
1976	Vedran Tuče	2003	2007		Bosnian Professor of clarinet, Academy of Music
1976	Amedeo Alessandro Raschieri	2004	2009		Italian Adjunct Professor in Latin language and literature
1976	Lorenzo Dalvit	2004	2010		Italian Associate Professor of Media and Cultural Studies
1976	Przemysław Marciniak	2004	2009		Polish classical philologist, byzantologist, associate professor
1976	Azra Aksamija	2005	2011	w	Bosnian Austrian artist and architectural historian
1976	Edward H. Huijbens	2005	2005		Icelandish cultural geographer
1976	Wasfi Shoqairat	2005	2006		Jordanian Associate Professor of English Literature
1976	Vito Carrassi	2005	2005		Italian adjunct professor in Comparative Literatures
1976	Taylor Petrey	2005			American Associate Professor of Religion
1976	Bakhtiar Sadjadi	2006	2010		Iranian Kurdish philosopher, academician, writer, and translator
1976	Luka Bekavac	2006	2006		Croatian Professor of Department of Comparative Literature

1976 Selcuk Artut	2006	2013		Turkish Professor of Visual Arts and Visual Communication Design
1976 Сергій Янчук	2006	2010		Ukrainian Associate Professor of the Department of Foreign Languages of the Chemical and Physical Faculty
1976 Sarab Abu-Rabia-Queder	2006	2006	w	Israeli-Arab sociologist, anthropologist, and feminist activist with a specialty in gender studies
1976 Benjamin Paloff	2007	2007		American Associate Professor of Slavic Languages and Literatures and of Comparative Literature
1976 Estanislao Sofia	2007	2013		Belgian historical linguist
1976 Giovanni Aloï	2007	2014		American art historian in modern and contemporary art (nature in art and art markets)
1976 Said Nasser Al Amrani	2007	2013		Omani Assistant Professor of Applied Linguistics
1976 Xanthé Mallett	2007	2007	w	British Scottish forensic anthropologist, criminologist and television presenter
1976 Zulkhumor Mirzaeva	2007		w	Uzbeki chief "Teaching methods of Uzbek Language and Literature" department
1976 Deirdre Fulton	2007	2011	w	American Associate Professor of Hebrew Bible/Old Testament
1976 Aleksandra Ippolitova	2008	2008	w	Russian literature critic (folklore)
1976 Hermassi Souhail	2010	2014		Tunisian assistant professor of Higher Institute of Sport and Physical Education
1976 Muthana Makki Mohammedali	2011	No		Iraqi Assistant Professor of Literature (English language and literature, Education, and History)
1976 Éva Pataki	2011	2015	w	Hungarian Lecturer, Department of English Linguistics and Literature
1976 Emmanuel Uba	2013	2015		Nigerian Lecturer at the Department of Languages and General Studies
1976 Mirela Voicu	2013	2013	w	Romanian Professor Music education
1976 Iram Rubab	2013	2019	w	Pakistani Assistant Professor, Department of Gender Studies
1976 Lonneke van Heugten	2013	No	w	Dutch Researcher Theatre & European Cultural Policy
1976 Hysen Kasumi	2014	2016		Kosovo Professor of English Language
1977 Claire Bower	1996	2004	w	Australian linguist (Australian indigenous languages)
1977 Aryeh Amihay	1996	2011		Israeli lecturer in the Dept of Religious Studies

1977 Saman Salah Hassan	1997	2013		Iraqi (Kurdish) Instructor of Literature (Women's and postcolonial literature)
1977 F. Zeynep Bilge	1998	2008	w	Turkish Asst. Prof. of English
1977 Meredith L. Patterson	1998	2005	w	American technologist, science fiction writer, and journalist
1977 Dr.Sadek Mohammed	1999	1999		Egyptian linguist
1977 Dagmar Abfalter	1999	2008	w	Austrian Associate Professor at the Department of Cultural Management and Gender Studies
1977 Kristina Killgrove	1999	2010	w	American bioarchaeologist, science communicator, and author who primarily covers anthropology and archaeology news and engages in research on ancient Roman skeletons
1977 Erik Petzell	2000	2007		Swedish Associate Professor in Nordic Languages and Academy Researcher at the Institute of Languages and Popular Memories
1977 Hanna Meretoja	2000	2010	w	Finnish Professor of Comparative Literature
1977 Andreas Kalkun	2000	2011		Estonian etho poet, musician and folklorist (Seto songs and religion)
1977 Ante Aikio	2000	2009		Finnish (Saami) linguist (history and etymology of the Uralic languages and the Sámi ethnolinguistic past)
1977 Nasir Uddin	2000	2008		Bangladeshi cultural anthropologist, post-colonial theorist, and prolific writer
1977 Adia Benton	2001	2009	w	American cultural and medical anthropologist
1977 Dr Bernice M. Murphy	2002	2004	w	Irish Assistant Professor; Lecturer in Popular Literature
1977 Jordynn Jack	2002	2005	w	American Professor, Department of English and Comparative Literature (Feminist Research in Rhetoric and Composition Studies)
1977 Miloš D. Đurić	2002	2012		Serbian Senior Lecturer in English Language and Literature
1977 Robert Östling	2002	2015		Swedish computational linguist
1977 Stiliana Milkova	2002	2007	w	Bulgarian Assistant Professor of Comparative Literature

1977 Yanai Toister	2002	2012		Australian painter, curator and scholar (Visual and Material Culture, Philosophy of Photography, CITAR, Ubiquity and Photographies)
1977 Philippe Matthey	2002	2012		Swiss Lecturer in History of religions
1977 Kris Heylen	2003	2005		Belgian linguist
1977 Mikael Roll	2003	2009		Swedish linguist
1977 Aynel Meshadiyeva	2003	2003		Azerbaijani Associate Professor, Academic Secretary Of Institute of Linguistics (Turkic languages and Theory of language)
1977 Slavo Krekovic	2003	2012		Slovakian musician, sound artist, musicologist, contemporary music and new media art curator, cultural organiser and non-profit activist
1977 Stefan Sudhoff	2003	2008		German linguist
1977 Vanessa Joosen	2003	2008	w	Dutch Professor English Literature and children's literature
1977 Голованева Татьяна	2003	2005	w	Russian philologist (корякский язык, корякский фольклор, автобиографические рассказы)
1977 Прокопчук Ольга Генриховна	2003	2003	w	Belarussian Head of the Department of Classical philology
1977 Giambernardo Piroddi	2003	No		Italian philologist
1977 Ge Wang	2003	2008		Chinese American musician, computer scientist, designer, author, and professor
1977 Wafaa El Beih	2003	2006	w	Egyptian literature critic (Italian literature)
1977 Adla Isanovic	2004	2017	w	Bosnian Associate Professor at The Academy of Fine Arts (multimedia)
1977 Alen Kalajdžija	2004	2013		Bosnian linguist, director of Institut for language
1977 Tar Gabriella-Nóra	2004	2005	w	Romanian Assoc. Prof. of German Literature (Hungarian theater and literature historian from Transylvania)
1977 Vikram Singh Amarawat	2004	2004		Indian Assistant Professor of History and Culture
1977 Anisa Avdagić	2004		w	Bosnian Associate Professor at the Department of Bosnian Language and Literature
1977 Antonio Río Torres Murciano	2005	2006		Spanish Profesor de Latín y Literatura Clásica (Latin, classical literature, medieval and Renaissance literature)

1977 Sandrine Sorlin	2005	2011	w	French Professor of English language and linguistics	
1977 Amila Ramovic	2005	2015	w	Bosnian the executive director of the Ars Aevi Project for Museum of Contemporary Art	
1977 Irfan Hošić	2006	2011		Bosnian Professor of Art History (modern and contemporary arts, design, fashion and architecture)	
1977 Jonathan Dettman	2006	2012		American Secretary Associate Professor of Spanish languages	
1977 Tijana Tropin	2006	2015	w	Serbian researcher of Institute for Literature and Arts (Children's literature, theory and poetics of translation, the fantastic in literature, genre literature)	
1977 Zsolt Gyenge	2006	2006		Hungarian freelance film critic and Assistant Professor in cinema and theory of visual communication	
1977 Clare Milledge	2006	2013	w	Australian lecturer at UNSW Art & Design (Anthropology, Art Visual Arts Installation, Painting)	
1977 Tanja Pavlović	2006		w	Bosnian Associate Professor of English Linguistics	
1977 Anil Joseph Pinto	2007	2013		Indian Associate Professor, Performing Arts, Theatre Studies, and Music	
1977 Pauwke Berkers	2007	2009		Dutch Head of Department of Arts and Culture Studies (pop culture of music)	
1977 Коденев Максим	2007	No		Belarusian cultural scientist	
1977 Jonathan Desen Mbachaga	2008	2014		Nigerian Lecturer 1 of Department of Theatre and Media Arts	
1977 Sindorela Doli Kryeziu	2008	2014	w	Albanian Professor of Albanian Grammar	
1977 Brent Nongbri	2008	2008		Australian specialist in the study of religion with a focus on ancient Christianity	
1977 Vikica Vujica	2008	2017	2020 w	Croatian Assistant, Department of Religious Sciences	1977-2020
1977 Elias K. Ng'etich	2008	2011		Kenyan Lecturer religious studies	
1977 Hamada Hassanein	2009	2013		Egyptian Assistant Professor of Linguistics	
1977 Joanna Stolarek	2009	2011	w	Polish academic teacher, editor, reviewer, translator in Anglo-American literature	
1977 Kati Kallio	2009	2014	w	Finnish Researcher, Finnish Literature Society & University of Helsinki	

1977	Michał Krawczak	2009	2011		Polish associate professor, vice-Director of Theater and Media Arts Department, program director and co-founder of Humanities Art and Technology Research Center
1977	Atle Ottesen Søvik	2009	2009		Norwegian theologian
1977	Karin Peter	2009	2010	w	Austrian Fellow of Department for Practical Theology, Religious
1977	Samuel O. Okanlawon	2009	2015		Nigerian Lecturer in Christian Theology
1977	Md. Kamrul Hasan	2010	2018		Bangladeshi applied linguist
1977	Arno Görgen	2010	2018		German medical culturologist (medical history, medical humanities, media studies and game studies)
1977	Teresa Proto	2010	2018	w	Italian Sessional Lecturer, Academy of Creative and Performing Arts (linguistics)
1977	Thorsten J. Pattberg	2010	2012		German philologist and cultural critic (The East-West Dichotomy)
1977	Thomas Hansen	2012	No		Danish Senior editor, Society for Danish Language and Literature
1977	Agus Heru Setiawan	2014	No		Indonesian Lecturer in Photography Department, Art Institute of Indonesia Surakarta
1977	Maryam Jafari Azarmani	2014	No	w	Iranian poet, literary critic, and translator
1977	Ivana Đerić	2014		w	Serbian Professor of English Language
1977	Hosea Kiprono Mitei	2014	2018		Kenyan Protestant Chaplain & Lecturer in Religious Studies
1977	Nazli Tyekçi	2016	No	w	Albanian Lecturer in Albanian Literature
1977	Andi Nur Faizah	2018	No	w	Indonesian Master Degree, Gender Studies
1978	Audrey Yue	1992	2001		Singaporean Professor in Media, Culture and Critical Theory
1978	Alexander Refsum Jensenius	1999	2007		Norwegian researcher (musicologist) and musician
1978	Jason Kandybowicz	2000	2006		American linguist
1978	Karel Vanhaesebrouck	2000	2007		Belgian Professor of theatre and performance studies
1978	Nadia Azevedo	2000	2006	w	Brazilian Speech Therapist (Brazilian Institute of Rehabilitation Medicine)
1978	Pinar Serdar Dinçer	2000	2016	w	Turkish associate Professor of art history (Early Christianity and Byzantine Arts)

1978 Sara Offenberg	2002	2008	w	Israeli researcher of Arts (Christian Milieu in Medieval Jewish Art and Literature)
1978 Sašo Živanović	2002	2007		Slovenian linguist
1978 Sebastian Pado	2002	2007		German computational linguist
1978 Liisi Laineste	2002	2008	w	Estonian senior fellow of Estonian Literary Museum (folklore, culture studies, humour studies)
1978 Muneerah Almahasheer	2002	2010	w	Saudi Arabian feminist, poet, Assistant Professor, Department of English
1978 Kristina Štrkalj Despot	2003	2007	w	Croatian Senior Research Fellow and the Vice Director of the Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics
1978 Nadine Akkerman	2003	2008	w	Dutch Reader in early modern English Literature
1978 prev. Schwager, born Scheiner	2003	2006	w	Austrian linguist
1978 Michal Temkin Martinez	2003	2004	w	American Associate Professor of Linguistics
1978 Sergio Muscat	2003	No		Maltese Graduate Student, Digital Art
1978 Bruno Nahod	2004	2014		Croatian researcher in Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics
1978 Felicity James	2004	2013	w	British Lecturer in Eighteenth and Nineteenth Century English Literature
1978 Laura Maes	2004	2013	w	Belgian sound art researcher, composer and sound engineer
1978 Földváry Miklós István	2004	2008		Hungarian Assistant Professor of Philology (liturgy, musicology, medieval studies, religious studies)
1978 Jelena Ivanisevic	2004	No	w	Croatian research associate (food anthropology, food studies, ethnology and cultural anthropology)
1978 Okeke Chukwuma	2004	2013		Nigerian linguist (semantics, Linguistics, Translation, Igbo Studies)
1978 Cynthia Clopper	2004	2004	w	American linguist and professor and chair of the linguistics department
1978 Dr. Dimitra Fimi	2005	2005	w	Greek Lecturer in Fantasy and Children's Literature
1978 Márta Abrusán	2005	2012	w	Austrian linguist (specialising in the study of meaning and language use)
1978 Masoud Dehghan	2005	2014		Iranian Assistant professor of Faculty of Literature and Foreign Languages (Theoretical, cognitive Linguistics)

1978	Rita Treija	2005	2013	w	Latvian folklore researcher
1978	Danijela Majstorović	2005	2005	w	Bosnian linguistics and cultural studies
1978	Sanja Berberović	2005		w	Bosnian Professor of English Linguistics
1978	Javad Zangouei	2006	2017		Iranian Independent Scholar in the Studies English Literature and Criticism
1978	Mustafa Bilge Satkın	2006	2006		Turkish lecturer of Fine Arts Department, photographer
1978	Titus Mpemba	2006	2014		Tanzanian Assistant Lecturer, Department of Kiswahili Language and Linguistics
1978	Alwin Kloekhorst	2006	2007		Dutch linguist (Indo-Europeanist and Hittitologist)
1978	Euripides Altintzoglou	2006	2010		Greek Course Leader (Photography), Senior Lecturer (Fine Art)
1978	Selma Kešetović	2006		w	Bosnian Associate Professor of English Linguistics
1978	Batoul M. Al-Muhaissen	2006	2013	w	Jordanian Doctor of French Language
1978	Joseph Lam	2006	2012		Hong Kong Assistant Professor of Religious Studies
1978	Hassan Kinyua Omari	2006			Kenyan Doctor in Philosophy and Religious Studies
1978	Md Shaikh Farid	2006	No		Bangladeshi Assistant Professor and Chairman Department of World Religions and Culture
1978	Lesong Cheng	2006	2006		Chinese Professor of Religious Studies
1978	Gian Maria Annovi	2007	2011		Italian poet, essayist, and professor
1978	Meliha Teparic	2007	2016	w	Bosnian Professor of Visual Art
1978	Sibel İzmir	2007	2014	w	Turkish Asst. Prof Dr, Department of English Language and Literature
1978	Vangelis Lympouridis	2007	2012		Greek director, producer and academic, MxR Studio, School of Cinematic Arts
1978	Vjekoslav Jukić	2007	2015		Croatian Art History researcher
1978	Alen Biskupović	2008	2014		Croatian assistant Professor in the field of theatre studies and a theatre critic
1978	Yasser Fouad Selim	2008	2008		Egyptian Associate Professor of English Literature
1978	Ivan Stacy	2009	2013		British Associate Professor of Literature
1978	Shahab Esfandiary	2009	2009		Iranian Assistant Professor, School of Film and Theatre
1978	Alin Suciú	2009	2013		Romanian coptologist and papyrologist
1978	Jeppe Bach Nikolajsen	2009	2010		Danish assistant professor at the Lutheran School of Theology
1978	Haytham Nawar	2010	2016		Egyptian painter, designer and researcher

1978 Ali Yigit	2010	No		Turkish researcher of English Language and Literature Department (Cultural Studies, Gender Studies, and Social and Cultural anthropology, comparative literature)
1978 Sara Andersdotter	2010		w	Swedish interdisciplinary artist, activist, curator and educator
1978 Iașișen Mihai Cosmin	2011	2011		Romanian sculptor, lecturer in Theatre and Visual Art
1978 Leonor Veiga	2011	2018	w	Portuguese Curator at ARTFEM, Women's Biennial of Art of Macau SAR Independent Researcher, Art Writer and Designer
1978 Oriol Fontdevila	2012	No		Spanish Independent curator and art critic
1978 Basil Ugorji	2012	2019		Nigerian President and CEO at International Center for Ethno-Religious Mediation
1978 Riaz Ahmad Saeed	2013	2016		Pakistani Lecturer, Islamic Studies
1978 Daria Karapetkova	2013		w	Bulgarian Associate professor of Italian language and translation
1979 Juliet McMains	1999		w	American dance scholar and instructor
1979 Guillaume Jacques	2000	2004		French linguist
1979 Travis Nygard	2001	2009		American Associate Professor of Art History
1979 Daria Khaltourina	2001	2003	w	Russian sociologist, anthropologist, demographer, and a public figure
1979 Kate Robson Brown	2001	2008	w	British anthropologist
1979 Konrad Juszczak	2002	2007		Polish researcher of Department of Psycholinguistics
1979 Mari Niitra	2002	No	w	Estonian director of Liivi Museum, semiotician, children's literature specialist
1979 Pippin Barr	2002	2008		Canadian Assistant Professor Department of Design and Computation Arts
1979 Vladimir Huzjan	2002	2010		Croatian historian writer and academic
1979 Sarah Parcak	2002	2005	w	American archaeologist, Egyptologist, and remote sensing expert, used satellite imaging to identify potential archaeological sites
1979 Andrew Mangham	2003	2005		British literary critic and Associate Professor of Victorian Literature and Culture
1979 Athanasia-Lida Dimou	2003	2008	w	Greek of Sign Language Technologies Team, Institute for Language and Speech Processing

1979	Khaled Khader Oraby	2003	No		Jordanian Lecturer of English Language and Linguistics
1979	Maša Grdešić	2003	2010	w	Croatian Assistant Professor (Department of Theory of Literature and Culture)
1979	Paschalis Nikolaou	2003	2006		Greek researcher in in Linguistics and Literature (translation Studies; theories of translation, the translation of poetry and the reception and poetics of literary translation, modernism and translation, (self-)translation and bilingualism)
1979	Sara Greco (-Morasso)	2003	2016	w	Italian Senior Assistant Professor of Argumentation
1979	Stefania Milan	2003	2009	w	Associate Professor of New Media and Digital Culture
1979	Ave Goršič	2003	2009	w	Estonian Researcher, Estonian Folklore Archives (Folkloristics, History of Discipline, Cultural Studies)
1979	Nathan W. Hill	2003	2008		American historical linguist and Tibetologist (languages of the Sino-Tibetan family)
1979	Ahmad Milad Karimi	2003	2012		Afghani-German philosopher of religion, scholar of Islam, translator of the Koran, and poet
1979	Brian House	2004	2016		American contemporary new media artist (more-than-human temporalities)
1979	Masood Ghayoomi	2004	2014		Iranian computanional linguist, Head of the Secretariat Office for World Universities's Ranking
1979	Nicholas Ng	2004	2008		Singaporean Post-doctoral Research Fellow (contemporary classical and commercial music, dance)
1979	Fatima Hadžić	2004	2012	w	Bosnian Musicologist
1979	Ieva Tihovska	2004	2014	w	Latvian folklorist
1979	Matthew Bowman	2004	2011		American the Howard W. Hunter Chair of Mormon Studies
1979	Susan M Kilonzo	2004	2008	w	Kenyan Associate Professor of Sociology of Religion
1979	Anca Cartîș	2005	2010	w	Romanian linguist
1979	Brindusa Grigoriu	2005	2010	w	Romanian reserarcher of French Languages and Literatures
1979	Fabrizio Macagno	2005	2008		Portugueze professor of philosophy (Argumentation, Pragmatics, Linguistics)

1979	Ieva Tihovska	2005	2015	w	Latvian researcher of folklore department (anthropology of music, ethnic minorities, Romani studies, popular music studies)
1979	Irina Tarsis	2005	2011	w	American Ukrainian born art historian and an attorney, director of Center for Art Law
1979	Julia Lajta-Novak	2005	2010	w	Austrian researcher and lecturer in English literature and cultural studies, literature curator, and poet
1979	Makokha Justus Kizito Siboe	2005	2011		Kenyan Lecturer of Literature Department (literary criticism, African Studies)
1979	Tran Ngoc Hieu	2005	2012		Vietnamese Lecturer of Literature (literary theories, contemporary art and Vietnamese modern literature)
1979	Cristinel Munteanu	2005	2006		Romanian philologist (etymology, dynamics and stylistics of phraseologisms, coordinator, editor and co-author of a book devoted to set phrases and famous formulae)
1979	Željka Babić	2005	2008	w	Bosnian Professor of English language/linguistics
1979	Camila Bechelany	2005	No	w	Brazilian Art curator and researcher
1979	Andrei Terian	2006	2014		Romanian Dean of Faculty of Letters and Arts and Professor of Romanian Literature in the Department of Romance Studies
1979	Harith Turki	2006	2009		Turkish Associate Professor of English and American Literature
1979	Natalia Igl	2006	2011	w	Norwegian Postdoctoral Fellow - Department of Literature, Area Studies and European Languages
1979	Paolo Gerbaudo	2006	2010		Spanish Lecturer in Digital Culture and Society
1979	Birgit Zotz	2006		w	Austrian writer, cultural anthropologist and an expert on the subject of hospitality management studies
1979	Zenaida Karavdić	2006		w	Bosnian linguist
1979	Khiara Bridges	2006	2008	w	American anthropologist specializing in the intersectionality of race, reproductive justice, and law
1979	Anne Helmond	2007	2015	w	Dutch researcher (New Media and Digital Culture)
1979	Marwa Talaat	2007	No	w	Egyptian fine artist
1979	Tom de Bruin	2007	2013		South African Senior Lecturer in New Testament Exegesis and Early Christian Literature

1979	Жучкова Анна	2007	2007	w	Russian literature critic (Russian and Foreign Literature)
1979	Kendra Coulter	2007	2007	w	Canadian labour studies scholar with a background in anthropology
1979	Demir Alihodžić	2007			Bosnian Associate Professor of English Linguistics
1979	Falk Hübner	2008	2013		Dutch composer, music theatre maker and researcher
1979	Jernej Habjan	2008	2010		Slovenian Research Fellow, Institute of Slovenian Literature and Literary Studies
1979	Mah Boon Yih	2008	2015		Malaysian senior lecturer at Academy of Language Studies
1979	Shreena Niketa Gandhi	2008	2009	w	British-American historian of religion, race, and empire
1979	Lucy Evans	2009	2009	w	British researcher in contemporary anglophone Caribbean literature
1979	Marietta Kesting	2009	2015	w	German Junior professor, Media & Art Theory (photography, film, cultural studies and media theory)
1979	Andreas Windmann	2009			German Literary scholar, essayist and writer
1979	Luca Govoni	2009			Italian teacher of food history and culture
1979	Zita Karkla	2010	No	w	Latvian researcher (literary studies, women's literary history, feminist and gender theories, digital humanities, women writers)
1979	Jelena Anđelković Grašar	2010	2015	w	Serbian researcher in Studies Art History, Gender Studies, and Visual art
1979	Mehmood ul Hassan	2011	No		Pakistani linguist (South Asian Literature in English & Postcolonial Studies)
1979	Anson Koch-Rein	2012	2013		American Assistant Professor of Liberal Arts (writer, editor and reviewer of scholar (gender studies))
1979	Wickham Clayton	2013	2013		British Lecturer in Film History and Theory, University for the Creative Arts
1979	Karen Keyhani	2013	No		Iranian Lectures on "Persian Regional Music"
1979	Bojana Mikelenić	2013		w	Croatian Research assistant, Chair of Spanish Language
1979	Nicolaus Janos Raag	2013			Swedish linguist, Coordinator, Forum of German Studies
1979	Amra Bosnić	2014	2016	w	Bosnian Assistant Professor of Music Theory and Pedagogy

1979 Ángel Nuño López	2015	2017		Spanish Profesor Filosofía de la Religión, Movimientos Religiosos
1979 Kaveh Oveisi	2016	No		Iranian film director and actor, lecturer Faculty of Art
1979 Gülce Arman Bayrakci	2017	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1979 Eirini Bergström Fournarakis	2018		w	Swedish MSc with a major in Religious Science
1979 Ilda Caeiro	2019	No	w	Spanish Predoctoral researcher in Cultural Antropology